

Production of the marine microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana* in pilot-scale thin-layer cascade photobioreactors using fresh pig slurry diluted with seawater

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ABSTRACT

The utilisation of effluents as nutrient sources is an interesting alternative for microalgae production as it reduces production costs and prevents environmental contamination. This work assesses the potential of producing the microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana* outdoors using pig slurry as the source of nutrients. The experiments were carried out in a thin-layer reactor operated in semi-continuous mode at dilution rates of 0.30 and 0.40 day⁻¹ during the autumn and summer, respectively. The biomass productivity ranged from 11.6 to 16.2 g·m⁻²·day⁻¹ in autumn and summer, respectively. The system was effective at removing N-NO₃⁻ (0.1-0.2 g·m⁻²·day⁻¹), N-NH₄⁺ (4.0-5.0 g·m⁻²·day⁻¹), and P-PO₄³⁻ (0.15-0.24 g·m⁻²·day⁻¹) from the pig slurry. The process was also able to reduce the content of pathogenic bacteria, such as total coliforms, sulphite-reducing *Clostridia* and *Salmonella*. Despite being able to grow in pig slurry, the use of this nutrient source led to a decrease in biomass productivity when compared to a medium of seawater supplemented with fertilisers. The eicosapentaenoic acid (20:5 n3) concentration in the *N. gaditana* biomass was 32 g·100 g⁻¹ of total fatty acids, for both autumn and summer, when using pig slurry as the nutrient source. The results suggest that the production of *N. gaditana* could be coupled with the biological treatment of pig slurry, allowing the recovery of nutrients while producing valuable biomass for the aquafeed industry. The resulting biomass, which has a high market value, complied with the requirements of the aquaculture sector.

Keywords: Waste management, circular economy, biomass, eutrophication, photosynthesis, sustainability.

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution and global warming have prompted scientific and commercial interest in microalgal biotechnology aimed at producing commercially valuable and sustainable products that can be used in aquaculture, agriculture, food production, cosmetics, and pharmaceuticals [1,2]. However, despite a large number of scientific

publications evaluating the potential applications of different strains and their optimal growth conditions, the number of processes that have achieved commercial success is very limited [3]. There is still a lack of research into the capacity of commercial-scale photobioreactors used to produce microalgal culture at low cost and over long periods of time [4,5].

High production costs are one of the main barriers for microalgae producers to overcome. According to Norsker et al. (2011) and Stephens et al. (2010), production costs are directly linked to the photobioreactor used and the biomass productivities achieved. Although raceway and flat-panel photobioreactors are the most widely utilised reactor designs for microalgae production at the pilot-scale [8,9], thin-layer cascade reactors have emerged as an attractive alternative. This type of system offers a substantial increase in biomass productivity [10], being 18% and 45% higher than tubular [11] and raceway bioreactors [12], respectively. In addition, thin-layer reactors have lower operating costs because their power consumption is less than other systems, such as closed bioreactors [13].

Nutrient and water requirements also contribute substantially to the total production costs. Several reports have highlighted the importance of using cheap and available nutrients in order to ensure commercial success. Microalgae can grow in different culture environments. This is beneficial because it allows us to take advantage of the nutrients present in livestock waste, such as those in pig slurry [14], and wastewater from industrial, household and agricultural activity [15,16]. Using the nitrogen and phosphorus that is naturally present in pig slurry as the sole nutrient source to produce microalgae has been previously reported [14,17]. This strategy is particularly interesting because pig slurry represents a huge environmental problem, so using it for microalgal biomass production would not only reduce its environmental impact but also allow a valuable product to be produced. Nevertheless, producing microalgae using pig slurry as a nutrient substrate involves the presence of potentially pathogenic bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *Clostridium*, *Salmonella* spp., *Listeria monocytogenes* and

Campylobacter, which exist in the pig slurry along with the microbial contamination that typically occurs when working in open systems [18].

The nutrient content in pig slurry (N-NH₄⁺ and P-PO₄³⁻) is exceptionally high and, therefore, it is important to regulate the slurry's nutrient concentration for optimal microalgae production. This means that the slurry needs to be diluted with water to allow microalgal growth. Approximately 1 m³ of process water is required to produce 1 kg of microalgal biomass [19]. However, there is a group of microalgae that can grow in seawater and therefore do not compete for freshwater resources. Among the saltwater microalgae, those of the *Nannochloropsis* genus are especially interesting given their rapid growth, high lipid content, and robustness, which means they can be produced in open reactors [20]. These microalgae can be used in the aquafeed industry as a natural source of polyunsaturated fatty acids [21].

Nannochloropsis gaditana has been produced outdoors at a pilot-scale in raceway and tubular reactors [22,23]. However, cultivating this microalga using thin-layer cascade reactors has not yet been attempted. Moreover, utilising pig slurry as the sole nutrient source to produce *N. gaditana* is a novel strategy that could reduce production costs and therefore facilitate its industrial implementation. The hypothesis of the present work is that it is possible to produce the microalga *N. gaditana* using thin-layer cascade photobioreactors at a pilot scale and using fresh pig slurry as the sole nutrient source. The goal of the process is to transform the nutrients. The main goals of this study included the assessment of the nutrient recovery capacity of the system and to identify if the microalga produced and accumulated polyunsaturated fatty acids, which are valuable for aquafeed applications.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Inocula and culture medium

The marine strain *Nannochloropsis gaditana* was used. The inoculum was maintained at 25 °C, pH 8.0, and 150 $\mu\text{mol photons}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ in batch mode until a concentration of 1.2 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ was reached, using the standard Algal medium for saltwater microalgae strains. The composition of the medium was 30 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ NaCl (artificial seawater) supplemented with 0.80 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, 0.35 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ MgSO_4 , 0.10 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ KH_2PO_4 and 0.03 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ of Karentol (Kenogard, Spain). The inoculum was scaled-up to pilot scale using 80 L bubble column bioreactors placed inside a greenhouse, with constant aeration and pH control (8.0 ± 0.1). The pH was controlled by the on-demand injection of CO_2 . In this case, the culture medium was prepared using natural seawater supplemented with nutrients, as described above, followed by sterilization with ozone.

2.2 Biomass production

Pilot-scale *Nannochloropsis gaditana* production was conducted at the SABANA demonstration facilities located at IFAPA (36°48'N, 2°43'W, Almería, Spain). The biomass production was carried out using both seawater supplemented with fertilisers and pig slurry diluted with seawater. Nitrogen is present in pig slurry mainly as N-NH_4^+ at concentrations above 150 $\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. The slurry used in this work was diluted down to 10% because N-NH_4^+ is toxic for microalgae at concentrations higher than 200 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ [24]. The N-NO_3^- concentration in the fertiliser-based medium was calculated using the N-NH_4^+ content of the slurry-based medium. Biomass production was carried out inside a greenhouse during the autumn and summer using a thin-layer bioreactor with a total volume of 2,400 L and an illuminated surface of 63 m^2 . In addition, the thin-layer bioreactor was provided with a 250 L bubble column with continuous air injection at a rate of 75 $\text{L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ to improve mass transfer and to desorb the gases (Fig. 1). The pH, temperature, and dissolved oxygen were monitored online using probes installed at the end of the channel. The environmental parameters (solar radiation and temperature) were likewise measured online. A SCADA system was used to actuate the pumps and valves inside the system. Before starting the semi-continuous experiments, the thin-layer

bioreactor was operated in batch mode for one week to allow the microalgae to stabilize under the new conditions. The biomass production was conducted operating in semi-continuous mode at 0.30 day⁻¹ and 0.40 day⁻¹ in autumn and summer, respectively. The pH was kept at 8.0 by the on-demand injection of CO₂ into the bubble column at 10 L·min⁻¹. The bioreactor was operated 24 h a day and semi-continuous operation was maintained until a stable steady-state was achieved, meaning that the biomass concentration did not alter for a minimum of three days and the total volume of the reactor was replaced at least twice. The daily evaporation inside the bioreactor was compensated for by adding freshwater.

2.4 Analytical determinations

Culture monitoring (biomass concentration and photosynthetic activity) was performed daily. The biomass fatty acid profile as well as the microbial count and supernatant determinations were conducted in triplicate during the last three days of the steady state. Briefly, the biomass concentration (*C_b*) was measured daily by filtering 50 mL of culture using 1 µm pore-diameter filters and drying the filtered biomass in an oven. The oven temperature was kept at 80 °C ± 1 °C and the biomass was dried for at least 24 h. The biomass productivity (*P_b*) was calculated as the product of the biomass concentration and the dilution rate (0.30 or 0.40 day⁻¹, depending on the season). The status of the culture was measured by means of the chlorophyll fluorescence ratio (*F_v/F_m*) using an AquaPen AP 100 fluorometer (Photon System Instruments, The Czech Republic). The optical density of the culture in the visible light range (400–700 nm) was determined daily using a UV–Vis spectrophotometer (GENESYS 10S, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Spain). The biomass extinction coefficient (*K_a*) was calculated by dividing the average optical density (*Abs*) by the product of the *C_b* and the cuvettes' light path (*p*; 0.01m):

$$K_a = \frac{Abs}{C_b * p}$$

The average irradiance in the photosynthetically active radiation range to which the cells were exposed in the culture (I_{av}) was calculated as a function of the irradiance on the surface of the culture (I_0), Ka , Cb and the light path inside the bioreactor (p):

$$I_{av} = \frac{I_0}{Ka * Cb * p} * (1 - e^{-Ka * Cb * p})$$

Moreover, the nutrient uptake was determined from the concentrations of nitrogen and phosphorus at the inlet and outlet of the bioreactor. The removal efficiency (Re) was calculated as the ratio between the nutrients at the outlet and the inlet effluents, using the following equation:

$$Re = \left[\frac{C_{in} - C_{out}}{C_{in}} \right] \cdot 100$$

The removal capacity (Rc) was calculated as the total amount of nutrients removed per time and culture volume unit, as shown below:

$$Rc = (C_{in} - C_{out}) * D$$

The nutrient content was determined using methods described elsewhere [25]. Briefly, phosphorus was measured by visible spectrophotometry through the phospho-vanado-molybdate complex. Ammonium was measured using the Nessler reactive method while the nitrates were quantified calorimetrically between 220 and 275 nm according to the standard method (4500-NO₃ B) using a spectrophotometer.

2.5 Microbial count

Once steady-state was achieved at the different dilution rates (0.30 or 0.40 day⁻¹, depending on the season), a microbiological analysis was performed to detect the microbial load and the potential presence of pathogenic bacteria. Mesophilic aerobic microbiota were determined by plate count using Nutritive Agar (PanReac AppliChem, Barcelona, Spain). Incubation was carried out over 48 h at 30 °C [26]. The samples were diluted to the 10⁻⁵ decimal scale using PBS. Each dilution was inoculated in triplicate into sterile and disposable Petri dishes. Total coliforms and *E. coli* were determined using Endo Agar (Merck, Madrid, Spain) as a differential culture media. The Petri dishes were

incubated under controlled conditions at 36 °C for 24 h. Sulfite Polymyxin Sulfadizine (SPS) Agar (PanReac AppliChem, Barcelona, Spain) was used as a solid medium for detecting and enumerating Sulphite-Reducing *Clostridia*. For this purpose, once the samples were inoculated on the plates, a layer of SPS agar was added to create anaerobiosis. In addition, the plates were incubated in an anaerobic jar with Anaerocult A (Merck, Madrid, Spain) at 44 °C for 48 h. Apart from plating, filtrations were performed to determine the presence of *E.coli* and Sulphite-Reducing *Clostridia* (1mL-100 mL) in the inlet and outlet waters of the reactors. The results were expressed as log CFU/mL. The presence of *Salmonella* was evaluated by inoculating 10 mL of each sample in a flask with 50 mL Buffered Peptone Water (BPW) for pre-enrichment at 37 °C over 24 h. A 0.1 mL aliquot was subsequently enriched in 10 mL of Rappaport Vassiliadis (RV) broth (Condalab, Madrid, Spain) at 42 °C for 48 h. Finally, each RV broth culture was plated onto Xylose Lysine Deoxycholate agar (PanReac AppliChem, Barcelona, Spain) to check for the presence of *Salmonella*. The samples were then incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. Kligler's medium (Condalab, Madrid, Spain) was used to confirm the presence of *Salmonella*-suspected colonies.

2.7 Fatty acid profile of the biomass

The saponifiable lipid content of the produced biomass was quantified by direct transesterification of the SLs to fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES). The content of saponifiable lipids as well as the fatty acid profile of the biomass were determined following a methodology describes elsewhere [27].

2.8 Statistical analysis

The results reported here are mean values of three independent experiments \pm the standard deviation. Differences between seasons and culture conditions were analysed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Centurion XVI Statistical software. The criterion for least significant difference (LSD) was in all cases $p < 0.05$. The relationships between the different variables were analysed using the bivariate Pearson correlation ($p < 0.05$).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Biomass production

Several aspects need to be considered when producing microalgae using large reactors and pig slurry as the nutrient source, among them the selection of: (1) a robust and productive strain with tolerance to variable nutrient concentrations and external environmental conditions, (2) a suitable photobioreactor design to provide the microalgae with their optimum growth conditions, and (3) an optimal dilution rate to maximise productivity [28]. In the present study, biomass production was carried out in the autumn and summer, operating the reactor at dilution rates of 0.30 or 0.40 day⁻¹, respectively. These rates were selected because previous studies had demonstrated that these values were optimal for these seasons [29,30]. The biomass productivity values are shown in Figure 2. Overall, biomass productivity was significantly affected by season, dilution rate and nutrient source ($p < 0.05$). Higher biomass productivities were observed when producing the biomass in seawater supplemented with commercial fertilisers, where the areal productivity ranged from 24.1 to 28.1 g·m⁻²·day⁻¹ for autumn and summer, respectively. However, when pig slurry was used as the nutrient source, the productivity was lower, ranging from 11.6 g·m⁻²·day⁻¹ (autumn) to 16.2 g·m⁻²·day⁻¹ (summer). The turbidity of the pig slurry and the presence of microorganisms and compounds could have limited microalgal growth. Indeed, a recent study by Ciardi et al. (2022b) noted that pig slurry turbidity could represent a problem in outdoor production systems. The productivities described were greater than those published by Grivalský et al. (2019) who used 660 m² thin-layer cascades for *Chlorella* production, carried out at a site located in Třeboň (The Czech Republic). They achieved average biomass productivity ranging from 14 g·m⁻²·day⁻¹ to about 17–18 g·m⁻²·day⁻¹ during the spring/summer period. These data demonstrate the influence of environmental conditions on microalgae productivity. In Almería, the environmental conditions are favourable for achieving high biomass productivities. In the present study, higher productivities were observed in the summer than in the autumn. This could be attributed

not only to the higher light availability in summer than in autumn but also to the dilution rate of 0.4 day⁻¹. As a larger percentage of culture was replaced daily with fresh media, nutrient and light availability were higher.

San Pedro et al. (2015) reported a lower maximum biomass yield (13.19 g·m⁻²·day⁻¹ at a dilution rate of 0.36 day⁻¹) using the same strain in outdoor raceway ponds under continuous culture conditions. Terigar and Theegala (2014b) found the highest biomass yield for *Nannochloropsis* sp. to be 43.4 g·m⁻²·day⁻¹ at a dilution rate of 0.16 day⁻¹ in an outdoor continuous-flow system. These studies were carried out using raceway reactors. The use of thin-layer cascade reactors to produce *N. gaditana* has not been attempted before although this photobioreactor design has been used to produce other microalgal strains. In a recent study, [30] found that *S. almeriensis* productivity in a single-channel thin-layer reactor with a culture depth of 0.02 m was higher than that in raceway reactors, where the culture depth was 0.14 m. These results were similar to those of previous studies reported by Morales-Amaral et al. (2015a) in which they demonstrated the higher productivity of thin-layer reactors compared to traditional raceways. In the present study, the Fv/Fm values ranged from 0.55 to 0.65 depending on the season, the dilution rate, and the nutrient source used (Fig. 2B). No significant differences were observed in the Fv/Fm values except for those obtained in the autumn when operating the reactor using seawater supplemented with fertilisers. The slightly lower values observed in the summer could be attributed to photo-inhibition caused by reversible damage to microalgae photosystem II [34]. The values reported here were within the optimal range for this strain, demonstrating that the culture was not subjected to any stress conditions and that the selected strain could grow under the operational and environmental conditions imposed.

3.2 Nutrient recovery

Nitrogen and phosphorus uptake is directly linked to biomass productivity. The lower the culture depth, the higher the radiation inside the culture and thus the higher the nitrogen and phosphorus removal [35,36]. Figure 3A shows that nitrogen removal from the pig

slurry was complete when the N-NO_3^- and N-NH_4^+ concentrations at the inflow were $0.1\text{-}0.2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ and $4\text{-}5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$, respectively. In contrast, when using fertilizer as the nutrient source, all the nitrogen was in the form of N-NO_3^- rather than ammonium, and it was not completely removed; the removal capacity was $2.9 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ (63%) for summer, and $2.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ (73%) for autumn. This does not mean that nitrogen consumption was higher when the media contained pig slurry; indeed, since most of the nitrogen present in the media was found as ammonia, it is likely that the high recoveries observed were due to stripping. Nevertheless, when the N-NO_3^- and N-NH_4^+ at the inlet increased, the consumption increased as well; this behaviour was observed in both media (Fig. 3A).

A similar trend for ammonium removal was published by Sánchez Zurano et al. (2020). The authors found that, using a thin-layer cascade reactor, *Scenedesmus* sp. can uptake N-NH_4^+ entirely from wastewater. The N-NH_4^+ consumption ranged from 0.75 to $1.53 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ (a depuration efficiency greater than 90%) whereas the nitrate consumption was lower than the ammonium consumption, ranging from 0 to $0.11 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$.

In a study by Şirin and Sillanpää (2015), *N. oculata* achieved 74% of total nitrogen removal when grown in municipal wastewater. In a similar study carried out by Sirakov and Velichkova (2014), *N. oculata* grown in aquaculture wastewater were able to remove 78.4% of the total nitrogen and 92% of the nitrate from the wastewater stream.

Phosphorus is an important macronutrient for the metabolism of microalgae because it can be incorporated into the biosynthesis of DNA, RNA or lipids through phosphorylation [40]. Phosphorus removal presented an opposite pattern to that observed for nitrogen (Fig. 3B). When produced using seawater supplemented with fertilisers, phosphorus removal was complete. This took place as a result of cell uptake; hence, the high phosphorus removal rate could be explained by higher biomass productivity. Şirin and Sillanpää (2015) reported a similar trend for *N. oculata* grown in municipal wastewater, where the total phosphorus removal rate was higher than 90%. However, when pig slurry was used as the nutrient source, not all the phosphorus in the media was consumed.

Thus, by applying a biomass balance, the phosphorus uptake varied from 0.15 to 0.24 $\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ for autumn and summer, respectively. It is likely that the culture was nitrogen-limited, and this led to the lower productivities observed. Moreover, the pig slurry might have contained heavy metals or other compounds that limited microalgal growth, but these were not determined in the present study. The results agree with those reported by Sánchez Zurano et al. (2020) for *Scenedesmus* sp. grown in wastewater using a 32 m^2 thin-layer reactor, in which the phosphorus uptake varied from 0.10 to 0.29 $\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ for autumn and spring, respectively. In addition, Figure 3B shows that phosphorus removal was higher in summer because of the above-mentioned higher biomass productivity. In addition, phosphorus removal presented a similar pattern to that observed for nitrogen removal; that is to say, when the P-PO_4^{-3} in the inlet increased, the uptake increased as well.

Consequently, looking at the productivity and nutrient removal results from the thin-layer reactor, it is evident that *Nannochloropsis gaditana* demonstrated robust stability over the seasons evaluated, with the removal capacity and productivities being especially influenced by the nutrient source and the environmental conditions.

3.3 Microbiological analysis

As mentioned above, the production of microalgae using pig slurry as the nutrient substrate entails the presence of pathogenic bacteria. Therefore, it is important to assess the main bacterial groups present when producing *N. gaditana* using pig slurry in order to evaluate the feasibility of the developed process. In the present study, we evaluated the aerobic mesophilic and heterotrophic bacteria count. This group of bacteria are widely distributed and are present in, for example, soil, air, animal/human bodies, and all types of water [41] along with coliform bacteria. Even though these bacterial groups cannot be used as indicators of pathogenic conditions, they do provide information about the microbial load present in the samples. The specific pathogenic bacteria that usually appear in pig slurry treatment include *E. coli*, sulphite-reducing *Clostridia* and *Salmonella* sp.. Microbial analyses were carried out at the wastewater inlets and the water outlets

(after removing the microalgae-bacteria biomass). According to the mesophilic aerobic microbiota, the microbial loads in the inlet wastewater (10% pig slurry) were similar in summer and autumn ($\log \text{CFU} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1} = 4.3\text{-}4.5$). The same occurred in the inlet seawater-supplemented media, having a constant value over the summer and autumn ($\log \text{CFU} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1} = 2.3\text{-}2.4$). With regard to the outlet effluents, a reduction was observed with respect to the microbiota detected in the inlets. According to the total coliforms, the values determined at both the slurry and fertilizer inlets were similar in summer and autumn ($\log \text{CFU} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1} = 2.4\text{-}2.5$). In the outlet waters, a significant reduction in total coliforms was observed, except when pig slurry was used as the nutrient source in summer. In terms of pathogenic bacteria, *E. coli*, sulphite-reducing *Clostridia* and *Salmonella sp.* were determined. *E. coli* was not detected in any sample (neither at the wastewater inlet nor at the water outlet). Similarly, *Salmonella sp.* was not detected in the inflow or outflow; nonetheless, it was detected in the raw pig manure (before being diluted with seawater). The seawater used during the trials had a concentration of $30 \text{ g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ of NaCl. Previous studies have indicated that enteric bacteria (such as *E. coli* and *Salmonella sp.*) are subjected to immediate osmotic shock under saline conditions. Their capacity to overcome these conditions could greatly influence their subsequent survival in the seawater [42]. Sulphite-reducing *Clostridia* was not detected in the samples produced using seawater supplemented with fertilisers whereas it did appear in the inflow and outflow from the reactor when using the pig slurry treatment. During the summer, the presence of sulphite-reducing *Clostridia* was measured in the inlet ($\log \text{CFU} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1} = 1.4$) and outlet of the microalgal culture ($\log \text{CFU} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1} = 0.3$). Moreover, these pathogenic bacteria appeared in the inflow ($\log \text{CFU} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1} = 1.8$) and outflow ($\log \text{CFU} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1} = 0.5$) of the trial carried out in the autumn. A significant reduction ($p < 0.01$) was observed in the quantification of sulphite-reducing *Clostridia* before and after the microalgae-based treatment. This reduction might be explained by various mechanisms such as the competition for nutrients, elevated pH and dissolved oxygen, the presence of algal toxins, or the adhesion and sedimentation of pathogens [43]. Specifically, the

removal of sulphite-reducing *Clostridia* (widely described as obligate anaerobic bacteria) is largely influenced by the high dissolved oxygen concentration reached during the daylight hours caused by photosynthetic activity, which implies that they cannot survive in microalgal cultures [44]. The absence of *E.coli* in the outflow samples means that the water resulting from microalgae production complies with Spanish regulations (*Real Decreto* 1620/2007).

3.4 Fatty acid content

One of the most important and interesting attributes of *N. gaditana* is its fatty acid content and composition. Special attention must be paid to the eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA, 20:5n3) content since microalgae from the *Nannochloropsis* genus are considered an important source of this valuable fatty acid. EPA is particularly interesting because of its health benefits [45,46]. Moreover, *N. gaditana* is one of the most extended microalgae strains used in aquaculture because of its fatty acid content and profile [47]. To compare the fatty acid production of this microalga when using different nutrient sources, it is important not only to obtain the highest fatty acid content but also the highest EPA concentration possible.

Figure 4A shows the fatty acid content (% wt of dry biomass) of the samples obtained using the two culture media studied. Figure 4B shows the EPA purity obtained in each case, that is, the percentage of EPA with respect to the percentage of total fatty acids. As shown in Figure 4A, the total fatty acid content of the dry microalgae biomass decreased as the dilution rate increased. So, for the two different nutrient sources studied in this work, the percentage of fatty acids measured in the samples taken in autumn, with a dilution rate of 0.3 day⁻¹, were higher than those obtained in summer with a dilution rate of 0.4 day⁻¹ (the pig slurry-based medium, 4.45 and 4.01% for autumn and summer, respectively, and the fertiliser-based medium, 7.94 and 4.66% wt, respectively). Other authors, such as Terigar and Theegala (2014), described similar behaviour and observed a decrease in the lipid content with increasing dilution rates in the *Nannochloropsis* sp. culture.

There were no significant differences in the saponifiable lipid content based on the nutrient source used or the season of the year, and therefore to the dilution rates. The saponifiable lipid content was lower than expected, when compared to those reported by various authors for microalgae of the genus *Nannochloropsis*, who recorded a fatty acid content of 12% with respect to the dry biomass [49,50]. In these studies, the cells were grown in outdoor tubular photobioreactors using fertilisers as the nutrient source. In any case, it is well reported that to increase lipid accumulation, it is necessary to grow the microalgae strains under stressful conditions, such as in a nitrogen-depleted environment, although under these conditions the biomass productivity will decrease [21]. Table 2 shows the fatty acid composition of the *N. gaditana* microalgal biomass under the different conditions studied in this work. As one can observe in this table, EPA represented 32.1% of the total fatty acids in the mixture containing sea water-10% pig slurry, confirming that it is possible to use this microalga under these culture conditions as the raw material for producing this valuable fatty acid. Authors such as Kowthaman et al. (2022) have compared several microalgal species in terms of their lipid content, highlighting species like *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Nannochloropsis* sp. and *Dunaliella* sp., among others. In any case, microalgae from the genus *Nannochloropsis* are often used as the raw material to produce lipids, especially EPA, due to their high biomass accumulation rate, successful large-scale cultivation and high lipid content [20,52]. Many studies have shown that this microalga adapts to changes in the culture conditions by modifying its molecular composition; therefore, the lipid composition strongly depends on factors such as irradiance, salinity, nutrient limitation or temperature [22]. Concerning the fatty acid content, species from the genus *Nannochloropsis* can accumulate 10-25 wt% in dry biomass [53] although this percentage depends on the culture conditions, as mentioned above.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study demonstrated the technical viability of producing the high-value microalgae *N. gaditana* outdoors using pilot-scale, thin-layer cascade photobioreactors and pig slurry diluted with seawater as the sole nutrient source. The studied strain showed itself to be robust and a promising candidate for large-scale commercial production, including in open systems. Despite being able to grow in a pig slurry medium, the use of this nutrient source led to a decrease in biomass productivity when compared to seawater supplemented with fertilisers. Higher biomass productivities were achieved in summer than in autumn. The treatment of the pig slurry using microalgae led to a decrease in the contents of mesophilic aerobic microbiota, total coliforms, and pathogenic bacteria, including sulphite-reducing *Clostridia* and *Salmonella* sp. The produced biomass was rich in EPA and other polyunsaturated fatty acids, demonstrating the potential of the produced biomass for use in the feed and aquafeed industries.

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Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interests.

CRedit author statement

Jiménez Veuthey, M.: Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – Original Draft; **Morillas-España, A.:** Investigation; **Sánchez-Zurano, A.:** Investigation, Writing – Original Draft;

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Table 1. Fatty acid profile (% of total fatty acids) of the produced microalgal biomass.

Fatty acid	Pig slurry		Fertilizer	
	Autumn (0.30 day ⁻¹)	Summer (0.40 day ⁻¹)	Autumn (0.30 day ⁻¹)	Summer (0.40 day ⁻¹)
14:00	3.4 ± 0.0 ^d	4.3 ± 0.1 ^b	3.9 ± 0.1 ^c	6.6 ± 0.0 ^a
16:00	19.7 ± 0.2 ^d	24.8 ± 0.1 ^b	21.0 ± 0.1 ^c	28.5 ± 0.2 ^a
16:1n7	15.9 ± 0.2 ^d	26.3 ± 0.3 ^c	30.2 ± 0.3 ^b	32.0 ± 0.3 ^a
16:2n4	1.4 ± 0.0 ^b	1.9 ± 0.2 ^a	2.0 ± 0.1 ^a	0.7 ± 0.0 ^c
16:3n4	1.6 ± 0.0 ^a	1.4 ± 0.1 ^b	1.1 ± 0.0 ^c	0.9 ± 0.1 ^c
18:00	3.3 ± 0.1 ^a	0.0 ^c	0.0 ^c	0.8 ± 0.0 ^b
18:1n9	3.5 ± 0.0 ^b	1.8 ± 0.0 ^c	1.5 ± 0.0 ^d	4.7 ± 0.0 ^a
18:1n7	1.7 ± 0.0 ^a	0.5 ± 0.0 ^b	0.6 ± 0.0 ^b	0.0 ^c
18:2n6	8.0 ± 0.2 ^a	1.3 ± 0.1 ^d	2.3 ± 0.0 ^c	2.5 ± 0.0 ^b
18:3n3	14.7 ± 0.2 ^a	2.0 ± 0.0 ^b	0.5 ± 0.0 ^c	0.0 ^d
20:4n6	2.4 ± 0.1 ^b	3.5 ± 0.1 ^a	2.4 ± 0.1 ^b	3.3 ± 0.1 ^a
20:5n3	32.1 ± 0.2 ^a	32.1 ± 0.3 ^a	32.1 ± 0.2 ^a	20.0 ± 0.3 ^b

Different letters in the same line indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$)

Figure legends

Figure 1. Photobioreactor used.

Figure 2. Effect of season, dilution rate, and nutrient source on (A) biomass productivity and (B) photosynthetic efficiency. Different lower-case letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 3. Influence of season, dilution rate, and nutrient source on (A) nitrogen (N-NH_4^+ and N-NO_3^-) and (B) phosphorus (P-PO_4^{3-}) removal capacity. Different lower-case letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 4. (A) Percentage of saponifiable lipids (% FA) with respect to the dry weight and (B) percentage of EPA with respect to the total fatty acid content of each sample.

Figure 1

Illuminated surface, m ²	67
Working volume, m ³	2.40
Culture: Depth, m	0.02
Culture: Velocity, m·s ⁻¹	0.2
Aeration, L·min ⁻¹	75

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

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